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SELF HELP GROUP –BANK LINKAGE PROGRAM: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY

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Abstract

The SHG-Bank Linkage Program (SBLP) was launched in 1992 as a flagship program by National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD). SHGs play pivotal role in socio economic empowerment of the rural people particularly the women folk. The basic research objective of the study is to study the performance evaluation of SHG-BL program promoted by the government under micro finance model. The research study is basically based on primary sources of data. The researcher also obtained the secondary sources of data. The researcher had selected 42 groups as sample size for this study. The researcher had made use of non probability convenience sampling technique. The researcher undertook the present study in khowang block of Dibrugarh district. This program is giving opportunity to the weaker section of the society to involve in various social activities, income earning activities and asset creation. But the performance evaluation of SHG- BL program is concerned, it is not up to the expectation which is evident from the present study.

Keyword: SBLP, NABARD, SHGs, microfinance, empowerment.

INTRODUCTION

The focus in the XI five year plan (2007-12) has been to build up the capacity of SHGs realizing the fact that these are in a more advantageous position to combine their resources and talents for enabling viable income generating activities, as compared to a lone individual efforts (Manga, 2011). The self help group-bank linkage (SBL) approach has the potential to make decisive impact on the security and empowerment of the most disadvantaged. The uniqueness of Self Help Groups (SHGs)

lies in the fact to a large extent they are self supporting self governing organizations, free from bureaucratization and politicization. The process empowers the poor and enables them to control direction of own development by identifying their felt needs (Rao and others, 2012). The SHG-Bank Linkage Program (SBLP) was launched in 1992 as a flagship program by National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD). The Program envisages organization of the poor people into SHG for building their capacities to manage their own resources and then negotiate bank credit on commercial terms (Singha, R.K.P.G., 2010). With policy support from Reserve Bank of India (RBI) and the Government, NABARD has been consistently and continuously spearheading the program by way of multi pronged and massive promotional interventions through almost all banks in the country and a large number of NGOs and developmental agencies (Mohanty, B.B., 2008). A Self Help Group is a registered or unregistered voluntary association of poor people of 15 to 20, from the same socio-economic background, involving primarily in saving and credit activities. A SHG is democratically without any political affiliations. It can be all- women group, all men-group or even a mixed group (Rao, G.V.J., 2010).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Some of the literatures have been reviewed in order to establish the strengths and weaknesses of various point in this regard. The reviewed literatures of the study have been given below:

Ramakrishna, H. and Khaja, Mohinudden, J. (2013) in their paper concluded that the SBLP has visionary objectives towards women and rural poor. It is necessary to have systematic mechanism in order to disburse all plans and projects. The study results proved that the SBLP is the best technique in poverty alleviation of the rural poor. The SHG members are highly involved in income generating activities and SBLP program has been effectively executed and evaluated properly. Dichter, Thomas (2007) in his article highlighted the social cohesion roles of pre existing informal safety nets and mutual aid systems, and suggested that by pushing more formal microcredit, we are hastening the demise of such systems. Paul, Susy (2011) in his study proved that SHG Bank linkage is a potent tool for financial inclusion and thereby inclusive growth. It is observed in the study that majority of the beneficiaries of SBL Program purchased productive assets/business assets in order to enhance their income generation and economic conditions which may result in economic independence of the beneficiaries and subsequently their empowerment. Subbarayudu, Y. and Haranath, G.(2011) in their survey concluded that both SBL and MFI model of micro-finance delivery have their own merits and demerits. If implemented efficiently, the SBL model of micro-finance would be much more superior to the MFI model. Kanniammal, K. and others (2011) in their empirical study concluded that the intervention of micro finance through SHG- Bank Linkage Program has positive impact on the economic and social status of the members especially the priory communities, in terms of increase in income, savings, employment generation, asset creation, decrease in dependency on money lenders, improvement in decision making skills, participation in community affairs and empowerment of women.

PROBLEM STATEMENT OF THE RESEARCH

SHGs play pivotal role in socio economic empowerment of the rural people particularly the women folk. The rural poor get socio economic empowerment through the SHGs. The SHG has emerged as a tool by giving benefit to the rural masses, thus fulfilling their needs and requirements in the recent years. Generally SHGs are formed by the likeminded people of homogeneous nature under various models. The SHG-BL program promoted by the government is one of the popular models and a large number of SHGs are performing income generating activities in the chosen study area. The performance evaluation of the group caste-wise category is essential for taking into account various parameters like involvement of members in group activities, amount of thrift, internal lending among members etc. The present study has made attempt to focus the performance evaluation of the group caste-wise under SHG-BL program.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The basic research objective of the study is to study the performance evaluation of SHG-BL program promoted by the government under micro finance model. The research has specified the evaluative performance of the SHG caste-wise category under the program.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

Primary Data: The present study is quantitative and empirical in nature. The research study is basically based on primary sources of data. For the collection of primary data, the researcher prepared an interview schedule containing mostly close ended questions in English. The researcher translated the interview schedule into local language so that SHG member having minimum qualification is able to read and understand the question of the schedule. It was administered to the SHG respondents by visiting them personally. The researcher recorded the response of the interviewee in the space of schedule himself. Apart from, the interviewer interacted with the respondents to collect more information for the study.

Pilot Study: The researcher also had made pilot study based on the constructed interview schedule from a few respondents by visiting field personally. Afterwards, the researcher modified the interview schedule to give final shape of it to collect the primary data.

Secondary Data: There are many sources of secondary data which are essential to collect in research study. The researcher made study of the secondary source to get idea in this field of research. The researcher also obtained the secondary sources of data from research article published in referred journal, research books etc.

Sampling Technique: The researcher had made use of non probability convenience sampling technique in carrying out the present investigation. The researcher had adopted the technique purposively on account of practical difficulties to use probability random sampling technique. The justification for the selection of the technique was that the SHGs become defunct for numbers of reasons and record of the defunct SHGs are officially unavailable in the block office.

Universe or Population Size: There are about 1126 SHGs formed for the period March, 2008 under SHG-BL program promoted by the government in the Khowang development block. Of these, 835 are I grade SHGs and 291 were II grade SHGs as per concerned block office record.

Sample size: The non probability sampling procedures do not claim representative of total population (Ahuja, Ram 2011). The researcher had selected 42 groups as sample size for this study. Of the sample group, the researcher had purposively selected two respondents from each group. The two respondents selected for interview consisted of either general member or leader of the group.

Locale of the Study: The researcher undertook the present study in khowang block of Dibrugarh district which is 35 kilometers away from the heart of the town. The justification for the selection of the block was that the development block is large in terms of geographical area and there are a large number of SHGs functioning in the area than others in the district.

Analytical Technique: After completion of field visit, the researcher started encoding, decoding and editing the collected raw data for the purpose of analysis to yield the desired result of the research study. The researcher had placed the data in tabulated form and analyzed the same with the help of percentage in discussion and interpretation part of the study.

Reference and Data Collection Period: The researcher had selected the SHGs functioning from the period 2000-2008 known as reference period. The justification of the reference period was that former was the starting period of SHG in the district and later period was taken into account to evaluate the performance of the SHG -BL program. The researcher had collected the primary data from the respondents in field personally during the year 2011-12.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

The present study is confined to a particular development block of dibrugarh district in terms of geographical area. The number of sample size is restricted to 42 continuing women SHGs for the

period 2000-08 under SHG-BL program promoted by the government only. Thus, the result of the study can be generalized in the study area merely. Moreover, the field study fully relied on sources of data provided by the respondents.

DISCUSSION AND INTERPRETATION

The performance evaluation of SHG-BL program is based on many criteria. The study had undertaken the performance evaluation of SHG-BL program caste-wise. Accordingly the study had classified the SHG into four categories: mixed SHGs, other class SHGs (OCs), backward class SHGs(BCs), schedule tribe SHGs (STs) etc. Discussion and analysis of the study included Distribution of SHG Member Households by Caste and Size, Caste and Age-wise Distribution of SHG Members, Caste and Education-wise Distribution of SHG Members, Caste -wise Distribution of SHG BY Membership, Percentage of Attendance of Members in Meeting by SHG Caste-wise category, Frequency Of Group meeting by SHG Caste-wise Category, Quorum of Members for a Meeting, Change of Leadership by SHG Caste-wise Category, Initial and Current Savings of Members in the Group, Accumulated Savings by SHG Caste-wise Category, Rate of Interest on Loan of SHG, Period of Savings Collection within the Group, Amount of Loan and SHG Members Caste-wise, Purpose of Loan and SHG Members Caste-wise and Maintenance of Records by SHG Caste-wise category etc.

Table 1: Distribution of SHG Member Households by Caste and Size

Caste Categories	Family Size			
	1-5	6-10	11-15	Total
OCs	06(07.14)	02(02.38)	02(02.38)	10(11.90)
BCs	48(57.14)	16(19.04)	02(02.38)	66(78.57)
STs	07(08.33)	01(01.19)	-----	08(09.52)
All	61(71.42)	19(22.61)	04(04.76)	84(100)

Source: Field Data

Figures in the Parentheses indicate percentage.

Table 1 presents the SHG member families in terms of household sizes. The family size was categorized into three 1-5, 6-10 and 11-15 respectively. Of these, the most members in the group were having family size of 1-5 members in category of OCs, BCs and STs representing 7.14%, 57.14% and 8.33% as compared to others. Thus, all sample SHG members family size of caste category of OCs, BCs and STs were 61(71.42%), 19 (22.61%) and 04 (04.76%).

Table 2: Caste and Age-wise Distribution of SHG Members

Age in years	Caste categories			
	OCs	BCs	STs	Total
20-30	02(02.38)	14(16.66)	03(03.57)	19(22.61)
31-40	06(07.14)	37(44.04)	02(02.38)	45(53.57)
41-50	01(01.19)	09(10.71)	03(03.57)	13(15.47)
51-60	01(01.19)	06(07.14)	-----	07(08.33)
All	10(11.90)	66(78.57)	08(09.52)	84(100)

Source: Field Data

Figures in the Parentheses indicate percentage.

Table 2 depicts caste and age wise distribution of SHG members. The age group of 20-30 years was 2.38 percent for OCs, 16.66 percent for BCs and 3.57 percent for STs Caste category. The members of SHG Caste category falling in the age bracket of 31-40 years were 7.14 for OCs 44.04 percent for BCs and 2.38 for STs. Thus it can be observed that member belonging to age of 31-40 years for OCs and BCs caste category is highest percent than other age group. But in ST members in age group of both 20-30 and 41-50 was equal percent (3.57).

Table 3: Caste and Education-wise Distribution of SHG Members

Caste Categories	Education Level					Total
	1	2	3	4	5	
OCs	-----	06(07.14)	01(01.19)	02(02.38)	01(01.19)	10(11.90)
BCs	04(04.76)	37(44.04)	16(19.04)	05(05.95)	04(04.76)	66(78.57)
STs	-----	05(05.95)	02(02.38)	01(01.19)	-----	08(09.52)
All	04(04.76)	48(57.14)	19(22.61)	08(09.52)	05(05.95)	84(100)

Source: Field Data

1: Illiterate, 2: Under matriculate, 3: Matriculate, 4. Higher secondary and 5: Graduate

Figures in the Parentheses indicate percentage.

The caste and educational qualification wise distribution of SHG members is depicted in Table 3. Most of the members were under matriculated showing 7.14, 44.04 and 5.95 percent in case of OCs, BCs and STs. 1.19 percent SHG members completed matriculation in OCs, 16 percent in BCs and 2 percent in ST category. Thus it can be concluded that the education level of SHG members was very low.

Table 4: Caste -wise Distribution of SHG by Membership

SHG categories	Number of Members					Total
	8	10	12	15	16	
Mixed SHGs	01(02.38)	03(07.14)	01(02.38)	-----	01(02.38)	06(14.28)
OC SHGs	-----	02(04.76)	-----	01(02.38)	01(02.38)	04(09.52)
BC SHGs	01(02.38)	25(59.52)	03(07.14)	-----	-----	29(69.04)
ST SHGs	-----	03(07.14)	-----	-----	-----	03(07.14)
All	02(04.76)	33(78.57)	04(09.52)	01(02.38)	02(04.76)	42(100)

Source: Field Data

Figures in the Parentheses indicate percentage.

It has been observed that 10 members constituted the majority SHGs (Table 4). 7.14 percent in mixed SHGs, 4.76 percent in OCs SHGs, 59.52 percent in BC SHGs and 7.14 percent in ST SHGs followed by 8, 12 and 16 members in 2.38 percent mixed SHGs, 15 and 16 members in 2.38 percent OCs SHGs, 12 members in 7.14 percent BCs SHGs, 10 members in 59.52 percent and 10 members in 7.14 percent STs SHGs.

Table 5: Percentage of Attendance of Members in Meeting by SHG Caste-wise category

SHG categories	Attendance percentage					Total
	60%	61-70%	71-80%	81-90%	100%	
Mixed SHGs	-----	02(04.76)	01(02.38)	-----	03(07.14)	06(14.28)
OC SHGs	01(02.38)	-----	02(04.76)	-----	01(02.38)	04(09.52)
BC SHGs	01(02.38)	01(02.38)	06(14.28)	07(16.66)	14(33.33)	29(69.04)
ST SHGs	-----	-----	01(02.38)	01(02.38)	01(02.38)	03(07.14)
All	02(04.76)	03(07.14)	10(23.80)	08(19.04)	19(45.23)	42(100)

Source: Field Data

Figures in the Parentheses indicate percentage.

Table 5 presents percentage of attendance of members in meeting by SHG Caste-wise category. All the members were present in most number of mixed SHGs (7.14%), 71-80% members were available in 4.76% OCs SHGs, Cent percent in 33.33% BCs SHGs and 71-80 percent, 81-90 percent and 100 percent availability of members recorded in 2.38% STs SHGs. Thus, it was found that attendance of cent percent members in the meeting of SHG is highest all caste category in the survey.

Table 6: Frequency Of Group meeting by SHG Caste-wise Category

SHG categories	Frequency of Group Meeting		
	Fortnightly	Monthly	Total
Mixed SHGs	-----	06(14.28)	06(14.28)
OC SHGs	02(04.76)	02(04.76)	04(09.52)
BC SHGs	08(19.04)	21(50.00)	29(69.04)
ST SHGs	-----	03(07.14)	03(07.14)
All	10(23.80)	32(76.19)	42(100)

Source: Field Data

Figures in the Parentheses indicate percentage.

Meeting of the SHG takes place to discuss many issues of operation in weekly, fortnightly and monthly. There was no weekly meeting held in the sample SHGs. Table 6 shows that meeting of mixed and ST SHGs took place in a month. Fortnightly and monthly meeting represented equal percent in OCs SHGs and 19.04 and 50 percent in BC SHGs. It is evident that holding of monthly meeting of SHG is the highest in SHG in all categories in sample SHGs.

Table 7: Quorum of Members for a Meeting

SHG categories	Quorum percentage			
	50-60%	61-70%	71-80%	Total
Mixed SHGs	03(07.14)	02(04.76)	01(02.38)	06(14.28)
OC SHGs	01(02.38)	03(07.14)	-----	04(09.52)
BC SHGs	15(35.71)	10(23.80)	04(09.52)	29(69.04)
ST SHGs	02(04.76)	-----	01(02.38)	03(07.14)
All	21(50.00)	15(35.71)	06(14.28)	42(100)

Source: Field Data

Figures in the Parentheses indicate percentage.

Table 7 depicts quorum of members for holding meeting of the SHGs. The quorum of member for holding the meeting was 50-60% for majority mixed SHGs, 61-70 % for most OCs SHGs (7.14%), 50-60% for most numbers of BCs SHGs(35.71%) and 50-60% for ST SHGs (4.76%). Thus it could be concluded that all 50-60% percent members constituting the quorum of meeting for all SHGs caste category.

Table 8: Change of Leadership by SHG Caste-wise Category

SHG categories	Leadership change		
	Yes	No	Total
Mixed SHGs	-----	06(14.28)	06(14.28)
OC SHGs	02(04.76)	02(07.14)	04(09.52)
BC SHGs	06(14.28)	23(64.28)	29(69.04)
ST SHGs	01(02.38)	02(04.76))	03(07.14)
All	09(21.42)	33(78.57)	42(100)

Source: Field Data

Figures in the Parentheses indicate percentage.

There is a system of rotation of leadership among the members of the group. Table 8 shows that there is no rotation of leadership in 6 numbers of mixed SHGs, 7.14 percent OCs SHGs, 64.28 percent in BCs SHGs and 4.76 percent in STs SHGs. There is rotation of membership in 4.76 percent OC SHGs, 14.28 percent in BCs SHGs and 2.38 percent in STs SHGs. It could be observed that no rotation of leadership in the group is highest percent all caste categories.

Table 9: Periodicity of Change of Leadership by SHG Caste-wise Category

SHG categories	Periodicity of Leadership Change		
	3 years	No fixed period	Total
Mixed SHGs	-----	06(14.28)	06(14.28)
OC SHG	02(04.76)	02(04.76)	04(09.52)
BC SHG	-----	29(69.04)	29(69.04)
ST SHG	-----	03(07.14)	03(07.14)
All	02(04.76)	40(95.23)	42

Source: Field Data

Figures in the Parentheses indicate percentage.

The periodicity of rotation of leadership by SHG caste wise category is shown in Table 9. It was found from the study that there was no fixed period of rotation of leadership in 14.28 percent mixed SHGs, 4.76 percent in OCs SHGs, 69.04% BCs SHGs and 7.14% in STs SHGs. Thus conclusion can be drawn that all sample SHGs responding no fixed period is the highest percent (95.23%) in the survey.

Table 10: Initial and Current Savings of Members in the Group

Caste Categories	Initial Savings of Members			Current Savings of Members		
	Below50	51-100	Total	Below50	51-100	total
OCs	12(14.28)	-----	12(14.28)	12(14.28)	-----	12(14.28)
BCs	56(66.66)	08(09.52)	64(76.19)	60(71.42)	04(04.76)	64(76.19)
STs	06(07.14)	02(02.38)	08(09.52)	08(09.52)		08(09.52)
All	76(90.47)	08(09.52)	84(100)	80(95.23)	04(04.76)	84(100)

Source: Field Data

Figures in the Parentheses indicate percentage.

Table 10 presents both initial and current savings of the members in the group. The amount of deposit was divided into two ranges: Below Rs. 50 and 51-100. In category-wise, the initial savings of members was 14.28% in OC category, 66.66% in BC category, 7.14% in ST category and 6% in ST category. Thus it could be observed that 90.47% all category is the highest depositing initial monthly contribution of Rs.50. So far as current deposit of members is concerned, 14.28% in OCs category, 71.42% in BCs category, 9.52% in STs made current monthly deposit below Rs.50. Therefore, it was found that members depositing below Rs.50 is highest in all categories. It is clear from the table that the monthly deposit of the members remained the same. Current savings of the members have not increased in the group and there is no improvement in savings of the members with the passing year.

Table 11: Accumulated Savings by SHG Caste-wise Category

SHG categories	Accumulated Savings			
	More than 5000	3000-5000	Less than 3000	Total
Mixed SHGs	04(09.52)	01(02.38)	01(2.38)	06(14.28)
OC SHGs	04(09.52)	-----	-----	04(09.52)
BC SHGs	24(57.14)	03(07.14)	02(04.76)	29(69.04)
ST SHGs	02(04.76)	01(02.38)	-----	03(07.14)
All	34(80.95)	05(11.90)	03(07.14)	42(100)

Source: Field Data

Figures in the Parentheses indicate percentage.

Table 11 depicts the accumulated savings by SHG Caste-wise category. Accumulated savings of the SHG was divided into three: more than 5000, 3000-5000 and less than 3000. The accumulated savings amount of more than 5000 were 9.52% in mixed SHGs, 9.52% in OCs SHGs, 57.14% in BC SHGs and 4.76% in ST SHGs. Thus it is concluded that accumulated saving of more than 5000 is the highest in all category than others.

Table 12: Rate of Interest on Loan of SHG

SHG categories	Interest Rate				
	2%	3%	4%	5%	Total
Mixed SHGs	01(02.38)	03(07.14)	-----	02(04.76)	06(14.28)
OC SHGs	02(04.76)	01(02.38)	-----	01(02.38)	04(09.52)
BC SHGs	01(02.38)	17(40.47)	02(04.76)	09(21.42)	29(69.04)
ST SHGs	01(02.38)	-----	-----	02(04.76)	03(07.14)
All	05(11.90)	21(50.00)	02(04.76)	14(33.33)	42(100)

Source: Field Data

Figures in the Parentheses indicate percentage.

The SHG charged interest on loan at certain percent from the members. Varying rate of interest on loan was charged by most SHGs. Accordingly 3% rate of interest was charged by majority mixed SHGs, 2% by most OCs SHGs (4.76%), 3% by most BCs SHGs (40.47%) and 2% by majority ST SHGs (4.76 percent). Thus it could be observed that all SHGs charging 3% rate of interest is the highest percent in the survey.

Table 13: Period of Savings Collection within the Group

SHG categories	Period of Savings	
	Less than three times	Total %
Mixed SHGs	06(100)	14.28
OC SHGs	04(100)	09.52
BC SHGs	29(100)	69.04
ST SHGs	03(100)	07.14
All	42	100

Source: Field Data

Figures in the Parentheses indicate percentage.

The period of savings collection from the member is presented in Table 12. The collection of saving from the members in the Mixed SHGs, OCs, BCs and STs is less than three times in a month. Thus it could be observed that members of all group categories collected the amount of contribution monthly.

Table 14: Amount of Loan and Caste -wise Distribution of Members

Loan Amount	Caste Categories			
	OCs	BCs	STs	Total
Less than 1000	01(01.51)	11(16.66)	03(04.54)	15(22.72)
1001-2500	01(01.51)	17(25.75)	02(03.03)	20(30.30)
2501-5000	04(06.06)	22(33.33)	03(04.54)	29(43.93)
7500-10000	01(01.51)	01(01.51)	-----	02(03.03)
Total	07(10.60)	51(77.27)	08(12.12)	66(100)

Source: Field Data

Figures in the Parentheses indicate percentage.

The loan amount of members is divided into four categories as depicted in Table 14. It was found that most SHG members belonging to OCs and BCs category representing 6.06% and 33.33% availed loan amount ranging from 2501-5000. The percentage (4.54%) of ST category availing loan of less than 1000 and 2501-5000 was the same. Thus it could be concluded that all categories of members belonging to OCs, BCs and STs taking loan amount of 2501-5000 is highest percent in the study.

Table15: Purpose of Loan and Caste-wise Distribution of Members

Purpose of Loan	Caste Categories			
	OCs	BCs	STs	Total
Household Purpose	02(03.03)	12(18.18)	01(03.03)	15(22.72)
Child education	02(03.03)	14(21.21)	04(06.06)	20(30.30)
Health Care	01(01.51)	12(18.18)	02(03.03)	15(22.72)
Financing Existing Business	01(01.51)	02(03.03)	-----	03(04.54)
Productive Purpose	01(01.51)	11(16.66)	01(03.03)	13(19.69)
All	07(10.60)	51(77.27)	08(12.12)	66(100)

Source: Field Data

Figures in the Parentheses indicate percentage.

The members of the SHGs availed loan from the group for doing various activities. Most of members made use of the loan for household purpose and child education showing equal percent (03.03) in OCs category. 21.21% and 6.06 percent members in BCs and ST took loan from the group for child education. Therefore, it can be concluded that taking loan for child education is the highest in all caste categories.

Table 16: Maintenance of Records by SHG Caste-wise category

SHG categories	Yes	Total
Mixed SHGs	06(100)	14.28
OC SHGs	04(100)	09.52
BC SHGs	29(100)	69.04
ST SHGs	03(100)	07.14
All SHGs	42	100.00

Source: Field Data

Figures in the Parentheses indicate percentage.

All the categories of SHGs maintained the records of books of account for financial transaction taking place within the group as depicted in Table 16. 100 percent of mixed, OCs, BCs and STs SHGs made use of account to record the financial transaction with the members and others which is a good sign of development in SHG-BL program.

SUGGESTION OF THE STUDY

The researcher had made certain specific suggestions based on the problem identified in findings of the study to improve the present performance of SHG-BL program.

The monthly contribution of the members has to be increased every year in all caste categories at a definite percent. In the meeting, every member should give one's own opinion regarding percentage increase of monthly contribution after giving thought. There must be consensus among all members about increased rate of monthly contribution and accordingly arrive at decision taking into account affordability of members to pay to the group.

The SHGs should pay attention to hold the group meeting frequently. There is a necessity to hold the meeting more on weekly basis in all caste categories. The leader of the SHGs is required to convey the message to all the members to hold the meeting frequently so that various problems of members are discussed and solved in the meeting.

The rotation of leadership should be followed in SHG. If one takes charge of leadership in the SHGs, one has to become active to run the group thus it will give everyone opportunity to learn and develop leadership qualities. It will result in increase the efficiency of the performance of the group activities.

It is advisable that SHGs should follow definite period of rotation of leadership. This is a part of discipline of carrying out the functions of the SHGs. All members need to understand this aspect and lay emphasis of rotation of leadership in a regular period of time.

It is suggested that in group meeting decision should be made to collect the monthly contribution from the members on weekly basis. Poor members will feel comfortable and affordable to pay small amount easily and they do not feel financial burden for the savings to be deposited in the group.

The SHG members should be encouraged to gain entrepreneurial knowledge. They have got less education and are jobless. Entrepreneurial skill will encourage them to set up micro enterprises of various kinds of income generating activities and asset creation.

The SHG member taking over the charge of leadership should participate in the leadership training program organized by government agency, banks and others to develop their skill. Good leadership qualities lead to operating the group efficiently and effectively.

The rate of interest on loan should be fixed in such a way that it is easily affordable to the members and source of income to the group. The SHG should charge reasonable rate of interest on loan offered to the members so that on the one hand, member is in a position pay the rate of interest on loan without difficulty on the other hand group can earn income from the loan.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

From the study it can be concluded that SHG-BL program promoted by the government functioning in the rural area is empowering the poor particularly the women folk. SHG- BL program is an instrument to develop the life of the poor women socially and financially. This program is giving opportunity to the weaker section of the society to involve in various social activities, income earning activities and asset creation. But the performance evaluation of SHG- BL program is concerned, it is not up to the expectation which is evident from the present study. There are many factors associated with poor functioning with the system. The SHG member involved in the system must understand government sponsored program and make attempt to plan to carry out the activities properly get success in the days to come.

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